

N.A.R

Ndoni Advanced Robotics

Company's objectives with a timeline for the future

Period of Time	Nr. of humanoid robots and machinery built and tested
22 nd century	1 Trillion
24 th century	2 Trillion
3 rd millennium	5 Trillion
4 th millennium	10 Trillion
6 th millennium	30 Trillion
8 th millennium	50 Trillion
10 th millennium	100 Trillion

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